

Synthesis of 1-Halophenyl-1H-Pyrazolo[4,3-c]Pyridines

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4-(*p*-Halophenyl-hydrazinonicotinic acids and 3-hydroxy-1-halophenyl-1H-pyrazolo(4,3-c)Pyridines have been prepared starting from 4-chloronicotinic acid and (*p*-) halophenylhydrazines.

MANY purine analogues and its derivatives have been prepared and tested but few of them have shown anti-tumour activity. Working on this hypothesis¹ that nitrogen atoms at 1- and 9-positions in purine (I) are essential for anti-neoplastic activity and nitrogen atoms at 3- and 7-positions are relatively unimportant, some 3-hydroxy-1-halophenyl-1H-pyrazolo [4,3-c] pyridines were prepared with a view to study their chemistry and biological activity.

4-Chloronicotinic acid² was the key intermediate for the synthesis of pyrazolo [4,3-c] pyridines³. Upon refluxing 4-chloronicotinic acid with (*p*-) halophenylhydrazines separately, 4-(*p*-) halophenylhydrazinonicotinic acids (IIa, b, c, d) were isolated. The acids (IIa, b, c, d) were cyclized to corresponding 3-hydroxy 1-halophenyl-1H-pyrazolo [4,3-c] pyridine hydrochlorides in presence of hydrochloric acid. Attempts were made to convert the above hydrochlorides into free bases (IIIa, b, c, d) but were unsuccessful, always a gummy product being obtained.

(7 ml.) was refluxed for 5 hr. Excess of ethanol was removed under reduced pressure. Yellowish solid was filtered and washed with little ethanol. The crude product on recrystallisation with ethanol gave an analytical sample (0.5 g., 71.4%) m.p. 233°-34° dec. Found : C, 58.5; H, 5.5. C₁₂H₁₀FN₃O₂ requires : C, 58.2; H, 4.05%.

IR spectrum (KBr) of the compound showed peaks at 3210 and 3320 cm⁻¹, characteristic of primary amino group.

3-Hydroxy 1-(*p*-)fluorophenyl-1H-pyrazolo [4,3-c] pyridine hydrochloride : 4-(*p*-) Fluorophenylhydrazinonicotinic acid (0.2 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (1 ml.) and distilled water (10 ml.) were refluxed for 5 hr. and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to one third of its original volume and cooled, yellowish solid separated out which was filtered and washed with little distilled water. The crude product was recrystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid, yield (0.11 g., 48%) m.p. 262°-263° dec. Found : C,

- (a) X = F
(b) X = Cl
(c) X = Br
(d) X = I.

It was also tried to prepare adduct of III(a, b, c, d) with picric acid and trinitrobenzoic acid but always a sticky mass was obtained.

Experimental

4-(*p*-) Fluorophenylhydrazinonicotinic acid (IIa) : A mixture of 4-chloronicotinic acid (0.45 g.), *p*-fluorophenylhydrazine (0.65 g.) and absolute ethanol

54.1; H, 3.6. C₁₂H₉FCIN₃O requires : C, 54.2; H, 3.4%.

Several attempts were made to convert the above hydrochloride into free base but were all unsuccessful, a gummy product being always obtained. It was also tried to prepare picrate of free base but again sticky mass was obtained. An intense band at 1635 cm⁻¹ was assigned to carbonyl group.

4-(*p*-) *Chlorophenylhydrazinonicotinic acid (IIb)*: A suspension of *p*-chlorophenylhydrazine (0.25 g.), 4-chloronicotinic acid (0.15 g.) in absolute ethanol (4 ml.) was heated under reflux for 6 hr. After completion of the reaction yellowish solid was obtained which was filtered and washed with little ethanol. The crude production recrystallisation with ethanol gave a pure sample (0.11 g., 46%) m.p. 228°–229° dec. Found: N, 15.6. $C_{12}H_{10}ClN_3O_2$ requires N, 15.9%.

Bands at 3220 and 3260 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum are assigned to primary amino group.

3-Hydroxy 1-(*p*-) *chlorophenyl-1H-pyrazolo [4,3-*c*] pyridine hydrochloride*: 4-(*p*-) chlorophenylhydrazinonicotinic acid (0.2 g.) was heated under reflux with the mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.8 ml.) and water (8 ml.) for 6 hr. The mixture was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to small volume and cooled, a brownish residue was obtained and the product (70 mg., 44%) recrystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid, gave an analytical sample m.p. 283°–284° dec. Found: N, 14.6. $C_{12}H_9Cl_2N_3O$ requires N, 14.9%.

Basification of the above hydrochloride with ammonia gave a gummy mass of 3-hydroxy 1-(*p*-) chlorophenyl-1H-pyrazolo [4,3-*c*] pyridine. Attempts were also made to prepare the picrate of free base but were not successful.

An intense peak at 1645 cm^{-1} , characteristic of carbonyl group was observed in the spectrum.

4-(*p*-) *Bromophenylhydrazinonicotinic acid (IIc)*: 4-Chloronicotinic acid (0.15 g.) and *p*-bromophenylhydrazine (0.3 g.) was heated under reflux with absolute ethanol (4 ml.) for 6 hr. Excess of ethanol was removed under reduced pressure. On cooling the flask a brown solid separated which was filtered and washed with little ethanol. Recrystallisation of the crude product afforded the analytical sample (0.14 g., 42%) m.p. 260° dec. Found: C, 44.9; H, 2.9. $C_{12}H_{10}BrN_3O_2$ requires C, 45.4; H, 3.5%.

3-Hydroxy 1-(*p*-) *bromophenyl-1H-pyrazolo [4,3-*c*] pyridine hydrochloride*: A mixture of 4-(*p*-) bromophenylhydrazinonicotinic acid (0.15 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.5 ml.) and distilled water (5 ml.) were refluxed for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to small volume. On cooling, yellowish solid was obtained which was filtered. The product (60 mg., 37.5%) was crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid,

m.p. 288° dec. Found: C, 43.95; H, 3.0. $C_{12}H_9BrClN_3O$ requires C, 44.1; H, 2.75%.

Basification of the hydrochloride gave a gummy mass which could not be solidified. IR spectrum (KBr) of the compound showed a sharp and strong band in the carbonyl region at 1640 cm^{-1} .

4-(*p*-) *Iodophenylhydrazinonicotinic acid (II_d)*: A suspension of *p*-iodophenylhydrazine (0.23 g.) and 4-chloronicotinic acid (0.16 g.) in absolute ethanol (4 ml.) was heated under reflux for 5 hr. After completion of the reaction yellowish solid obtained was filtered and washed with little ethanol. The production recrystallisation with ethanol gave a pure sample (0.15 g., 43%) m.p. 195°–196°. Found: N, 11.5. $C_{12}H_{10}IN_3O_2$ requires N, 11.8%.

3-Hydroxy 1-(*p*-) *iodophenyl-1H-pyrazolo [4,3-*c*] pyridine hydrochloride*: 4-(*p*-) Iodophenylhydrazinonicotinic acid (0.2 g.) was heated under reflux with concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.8 ml.) and distilled water (8 ml.) for 6 hr. After cooling, the reaction content was filtered, concentrated to small volume and cooled. A blackish residue was obtained which was crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid. Recrystallisation of the product gave an analytical sample (65 mg., 32%) m.p. 310° dec. Found: N, 10.85. $C_{12}H_9ClIN_3O$ requires N, 11.2%.

The above hydrochloride was basified with ammonia to convert it into free base but a gummy mass was always obtained. Attempts were made to prepare adduct with trinitrobenzoic acid but were unsuccessful.

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